

Factors Related to the Wound Healing Process in Post-Appendectomy Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Appendectomy is an abdominal surgery due to inflammation of the appendix. The importance of taking care of post appendectomy patients is to help the wound healing process, reduce the risk of infection in the wound and prevent post appendectomy complications. Many factors affect the wound healing process in post appendectomy patients such as age, anemia, comorbidities, vascularization, obesity nutrition, drugs, smoking, early mobilization, personal hygiene and stress.

Purpose: Knowing the factors that influence the wound healing process in post appendectomy patients

Method: The design of this study is analytic observational using a cross sectional approach, namely data collection of independent and dependent variables is carried out simultaneously. The sampling technique in this study was total sampling with a sample size of 50. This research was conducted in 3 hospitals in Pasaman, West Sumatra Province, namely in the Surgical Inpatient Room of TIB Hospital, Ibnu Sina Panti, and Tuanku Rao Pasaman Hospital. The analysis used was bivariate analysis with Chi-square test and Multivariate Analysis with multiple logistic regression.

Result: The results showed that nutritional factors had a significant relationship with the post appendectomy wound healing process with a p value (0.013), the early mobilization factor also had a significant relationship with post appendectomy wound healing with a p value (0.021) and the anemia factor also had a significant relationship with the post appendectomy wound healing process with a p value (0.016). However, there was one factor that did not have a significant relationship with the post appendectomy wound healing process, namely the wound hygiene factor. Multivariate results showed that the most dominant factor influencing the post appendectomy wound healing process was anemia.

Conclusion: Anemia is the most dominant factor in the wound healing process because it is systemic. If the patient has severe anemia, indirectly the patient will not be able to perform early mobilization, perform personal hygienics, the patient's immunity will weaken so that it will be easily infected and will affect the post appendectomy wound healing process. It is often found that post op patients are unable to move due to possible postoperative complications and activity restrictions, so that the patient's physical capacity is at risk of decreasing. To maintain optimal conditions despite limitations, patients are required to continue to be able to independently perform self-care. It is hoped that nurses in hospitals will be able to apply self-care theory to post appendectomy patients so as to reduce the number of post appendectomy complications and deaths.

Keywords: Appendectomy, wound healing factors, Wound healing process

INTRODUCTION

Appendicitis is an acute inflammation of the vermiform appendix and is the most common cause of emergency abdominal surgery (Rizky Ananda et al., 2021). Appendicitis is a condition in which infection occurs in the appendix. Mild cases can resolve without treatment, but many cases require laparotomy with removal of the infected appendix (Zacharzewska-Gondek et al., 2019). If left untreated, the mortality rate is quite high due to peritonitis and shock when the infected appendix ruptures (Widodo & Qoniah, 2020). Appendicitis, or inflammation of the appendix, is a

common intra-abdominal infection in developed countries, while the incidence is lower in developing countries. This may be related to the low fiber diet in modern (urban) communities compared to rural communities with a high fiber intake (Ghaly et al., 2021). According to the World Health Organization in 2018, appendectomy is the most frequently performed abdominal surgery in the United States. The number of 734,138 people in 2017 increased to 739,117 people in 2018. In Asia, the incidence of Appendicitis in 2013 was 4.8% of the total population. Meanwhile, from the results of the Household Health Survey (SKRT) in

Indonesia in 2016, the number of Appendicitis sufferers in Indonesia reached 591,819 people and increased in 2017 by 596,132 people, while in West Sumatra there were 2310 cases of Appendicitis per year (Wainsani & Khoiriyah, 2020). In Pasaman Regency, Appendicitis cases are more common in young people between 8-25 years old, around 60%, and around 30% of those aged <65 years and around 19% of those aged >65 years (Tuanku Imam Bonjol Regional General Hospital Management Information System (SIMRSUD 2024).

If inflammation of the appendix is not promptly treated or acted upon, the appendix will rupture, and the ruptured intestine can allow bacteria to enter the intestine, causing peritonitis which can be fatal and can form an abscess in the intestine (Murwaningsih & Waluyo, 2021). A common complication is perforated appendicitis which can cause an abscess, requiring an appendectomy (Kheru et al., 2022). An appendectomy is a surgical procedure that removes the appendix to reduce the risk of perforation (Roza et al., 2023). Appendectomy causes a post-operative wound that takes time to heal and requires ongoing care (WHO, 2024).

The wound healing process is a complex process consisting of 3 phases, namely the Inflammatory Phase which is divided into early inflammation (hemostasis phase), and late inflammation which occurs from day 0 to day 4 after injury. The Proliferation Phase which includes three main processes, namely: Neoangiogenesis, fibroblast formation and re-epithelialization, occurs from day 3 to day 21 after injury. The Maturation Phase occurs from day 21 to 1 year after injury which aims to maximize the strength and structural integrity of new wound-filling tissue, epithelial growth and scar tissue formation (Brunner & Suddarth, 2017). The factors related to wound healing include age, anemia, comorbidities, vascularization, obesity nutrition, medications, smoking, early mobilization, personal hygiene and stress (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022). Based on the description above, the purpose of this study is to determine the factors related to the post-appendectomy wound healing process.

METHOD

This study will be conducted to determine the factors associated with the wound healing process in post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024. The study design is an observational analytic study using a cross-sectional approach, namely Data collection for independent and dependent variables is carried out simultaneously (Notoatmodjo, 2015).

Population is the whole and a variable related to the problem being studied (Sugiyono, 2017). The population in this study was all post-op appendectomy

patients treated in the surgical room of Tuanku Imam Bonjol Hospital, Ibnu Sina Panti Hospital, and Tuanku Rao Hospital, Pasaman. The average number of patients per month at Tuanku Imam Bonjol Hospital is around 20-25 patients, Ibnu Sina Panti Hospital around 10-15 patients and Tuanku Rao Hospital around 5-10 patients per month. The sample is a portion taken from the entire object being studied and is considered representative of the entire population (Sugiyono, 2017). Inclusion criteria are the general characteristics of research subjects from an accessible target population to be studied. Scientific considerations should be the guideline in determining inclusion criteria (Sugiyono, 2018).

The sample characteristics that can be included in the inclusion criteria in this study include: First day post-op patients, patients willing to be respondents, patients with Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) 14-15. In this study, the sample researchers used was 50 samples taken based on the criteria of Roscoe (1975) namely sample size between 30-500 elements, if the sample is divided again into sub samples, the minimum number of samples must be 30, in multivariate research including using multivariate regression analysis the number of samples must be 10 times greater than the number of variables. In this study the number of independent variables is 4 and the dependent variable is 1 so the total sample in this study is 50 samples.

Data collection was conducted by first providing prospective respondents with an explanation of the purpose, methods, and objectives of the study. Respondents were given the opportunity to ask questions if there was anything they did not understand from the explanation. Respondents who wanted to participate were asked to sign an informed consent form. The researcher then conducted observations and interviews regarding the factors being studied, while marking the observations on the observation sheet. Data collection was conducted from the first post-op day until the seventh day. If the patient returned home before the seventh day, the researcher contracted with the respondent to conduct a home visit until the seventh post-op day.

Bivariate data analysis used the chi-square test. To determine the significance of the statistical calculations, a significance threshold of 0.05 was used. If $p \leq 0.05$, it is considered statistically significant, and if $p > 0.05$, it is considered insignificant. To determine the most dominant factors influencing post-appendectomy wound healing, multiple logistic regression analysis was performed.

Results

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Factors Associated with Post-Appendectomy Wound Healing in Pasaman in 2024

No	Variabel	n	%
1	Nutritional Status		
	Ideal	33	66
	Less than Ideal	17	34
	Number	50	100
2	Wound Cleanliness		
	Clean	41	82
	Dirty	9	19
	Number	50	100
3	Early Mobilization		
	Good	28	56
	Not Good	22	44
	Number	50	100
4.	Anemia		
	Anemia	19	38
	Not Anemic	31	62
	Number	50	100

Based on Table.1 above, it was found that more than half of the 33 respondents (66%) had ideal nutritional status and only a small portion of 17 respondents (34%) had less than ideal nutritional status. In the wound hygiene factor, most of the 41 respondents (82%) had clean wounds and a small portion of 9 respondents (19%) had dirty wounds. In the early mobilization factor, more than half of the 28 respondents (56%) had good mobilization and less than half of the 22 respondents (44%) had poor mobilization. In the anemia factor, it was found that most of the 31 respondents (62%) did not experience anemia and a small portion of 19 respondents (38%) experienced anemia.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Wound Healing Process in Post-Appendectomy Patients in Pasaman in 2024

Wound Healing Process	N	%
Good	28	56
Not Good	22	44
Number	50	100

Based on Table 2 above, it was found that more than half of the 28 respondents (56%) had a good wound healing process, and less than half of the 22 respondents (44%) had a poor post-appendectomy wound healing process.

Table 3. Relationship between Nutritional Status Factors and the Post-Appendectomy Wound Healing Process in Pasaman in 2024

Nutritional Status	Wound Healing Process				P Value	OR		
	Good		Not Good				Total	
	n	%	n	%			Jumlah	%
Good	18	54,5	15	45,5	33	100	0,013	9,840
Not Good	10	58,8	7	41,2	17	100		
Total	28	56	22	44	50	100		

Based on table 3 above, it can be seen that from 33 respondents whose nutritional status factor is good, there are 18 respondents (54.5%) whose wound healing process is good, while from 17 respondents whose nutritional status is poor, there are 10 respondents (58.8%) whose healing process is good. The results of the statistical test obtained that the p-

value (0.013) then statistically stated that there is a significant relationship between nutritional status factors and the wound healing process of post-op appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024. This relationship is also strengthened by the Odds Ratio (OR) value which has an opportunity where $OR = 9,840$ which means that post-op appendectomy patients who have good nutrition have a 9-10 times chance of a good wound healing process.

Table 4. Relationship between wound hygiene factors and the wound healing process in post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024

Wound Hygiene Factors	Wound Healing Process						P Value	OR
	Good		Not Good		Total			
	n	%	n	%	Jumlah	%		
Clean	18	43,9	23	56,1	41	100	0,976	1,002
Dirty	4	44,4	5	55,6	9	100		
Total	22	44	28	56	50	100		

Based on table 4 above, it was found that 41 respondents whose wound hygiene was clean, there were 23 respondents (56.1%) whose wound healing process was good, while from 9 respondents whose wound hygiene was dirty, there were 5 respondents (55.6%) whose healing process was not good. The results of the statistical test showed that the p-value (0.976) means that statistically there is no significant relationship between wound hygiene factors and the wound healing process of post-op appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024. This relationship is also strengthened by the Odds Ratio (OR) value which has a chance where $OR = 1.002$ which means that post-op appendectomy patients whose wound hygiene is dirty will have a risk of 1 time for a poor wound healing process.

Table 5. Relationship between Early Mobilization Factors and the wound healing process in post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024

Early Mobilization Factors	Wound Healing Process						P Value	OR
	Good		Not Good		Total			
	n	%	n	%	Jumlah	%		
Good	14	50	14	50	41	100	0,021	1,750
Not Good	8	36,4	14	63,6	9	100		
Total	22	44	28	56	50	100		

Based on table 5 above, it can be seen that of the 28 respondents whose early mobilization factors were not good, there were 14 respondents (50.0%) whose wound healing process was not good, while of the 22 respondents whose mobilization factors were good, there were 14 respondents (50%) whose healing process was also good. The results of the statistical test obtained that the p-value (0.021) then statistically stated that there was a significant relationship between the early mobilization factor and the wound healing process in post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024. This relationship was also strengthened by the Odds Ratio (OR) value which had an opportunity where $OR = 1.750$ which means that post-op appendectomy patients who had good early mobilization had a 1-2 times chance of a good wound healing process.

Table 6. Relationship between anemia factors and the wound healing process in post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024

Anemia Factor	Wound Healing Process						P Value	OR
	Good		Not Good		Total			
	n	%	n	%	Jumlah	%		
Anemia	9	47,4	10	52,6	19	100	0,016	1,759
Not Anemic	19	61,3	12	38,7	31	100		
Total	28	56	22	44	50	100		

Based on Table 6 above, it can be seen that of the 31 respondents who were not anemic, there were 19 respondents (61.3%) whose wound healing process was good, while of the 19 respondents who were anemic, there were 10 respondents (52.6%) whose healing process was not good. The results of the statistical test obtained that the p-value (0.016) then statistically stated that there was a significant relationship between the anemia factor and the wound healing process in post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024. This relationship was also strengthened by the Odds Ratio (OR) value which had an opportunity where OR = 1.759 which means that post-op appendectomy patients who were not anemic had a 1-2 times chance of a good wound healing process.

Table 7. Distribution of Step1 Test Results on Variable Factors Related to the Wound Healing Process in Post-Appendectomy Patients in Pasaman in 2024

Step variable	Score	Df	p-value	OR
Nutritional Status Factors	0.083	1	0.013	9.840
Hygiene Factors	0.001	1	0.976	1.022
Mobilization Factors	0.930	1	0.021	1.750
Anemia Factors	0.927	1	0.016	1.759
Overall statistic	1.693	4	0.792	14.371

Based on Table 7 above, it can be seen that after conducting the step 1 test (nutritional status, wound cleanliness, early mobilization and anemia), an overall value of 1.693 with OR = 14.371 was obtained, so looking at these factors, the wound cleanliness factor will be deleted from other factors as a supporting factor with a p-value (0.930) in the wound healing process.

Table 8. Distribution of Step2 Test Results on Variable Factors Related to the Wound Healing Process in Post-Appendectomy Patients in Pasaman in 2024

Step variable	SE	Wald	Df	p-value	OR	95% CI Lower	for OR Upper
Nutritional Status	0.616	0.134	1	0.014	6.798	0.239	2.670
Early Mobilization	0.596	0.655	1	0.020	5.617	0.192	1.986
Anemia	0.603	0.652	1	0.009	7.628	0.499	5.310
Constant	0.366	0.246	1	0.620	1.422		

Based on Table 8 above, it can be seen that of the 3 factors that still have an influence, the most dominant factor in the wound healing process is the anemia factor with a p-value = 0.009 with a probability of OR = 7.628, which means that there is a dominant relationship (Binary Logistic Regression) between the anemia factor and the wound healing process of post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024.

DISCUSSION

The study results showed that more than half of the 18 (54.5%) respondents with good nutritional status experienced good wound healing. A statistical test showed a p -value (0.013) < 0.05 , indicating a significant relationship between nutritional status and wound healing. This relationship was further strengthened by the Odds Ratio (OR) value, which showed an OR of 9.840, indicating that post-appendectomy patients with good nutrition had a 9-10 times greater chance of good wound healing in Pasaman in 2024. These results are relevant to the study by Arribas-López et al. (2021), which states that there is a significant relationship between nutritional status and wound healing. Under stressful conditions, metabolic nutrient needs increase, which, if not met, can slow or even halt wound healing, leading to chronic wounds. Siswandi et al.'s (2020) research also found a significant relationship between nutritional status and post-appendectomy wound healing, as nutritional status directly impacts a person's health. Deng et al. (2021) stated that nutrition is a determining factor in the wound healing process, especially in patients with chronic diseases such as diabetes mellitus.

According to Ghaly et al. (2021), wound care and healing are influenced by various factors, one of which is nutrition. Consuming food that does not meet the body's nutritional needs, both in terms of quantity and quality, will impact the wound healing process. If adequate nutrition is not met, the wound healing process will be hampered, the risk of infection will increase, problems will arise, and treatment will take longer. Malnutrition, especially protein deficiency, has a significant impact on wound healing. In addition to nutrients containing protein, which aids wound healing, protein sources can be obtained from animal protein and plant protein. Animal protein includes eggs, meat, fish, shrimp, milk, and cheese. Meanwhile, plant protein is found in abundance in tofu, tempeh, nuts, corn, and others. Wound healing is also influenced by fat and carbohydrates (Murwaningsih & Waluyo, 2021).

Nutrition is the process of utilizing normally consumed food through digestion, absorption, transportation, storage, metabolism, and excretion of unused substances to maintain life, growth, and normal organ function, as well as to produce energy. Optimal nutritional status plays a crucial role in influencing the wound healing process, including post-operative wounds. Wound healing is a complex series of stages involving various biological mechanisms, such as cell regeneration, new tissue formation, and collagen formation. Good nutritional status provides essential support for the body to carry out these processes efficiently. Conversely, nutritional deficiencies or poor nutritional status can reduce the body's ability to heal

wounds, increase the risk of infection, and prolong healing time (Sumarwati et al., 2022).

Based on the results of the study, it was found that more than half of the 23 (56.1%) respondents who had clean wounds experienced a good wound healing process, while 5 of 9 respondents (55.6%) whose wound cleanliness was dirty experienced a good wound healing process as well. The results of the statistical test obtained a p -value (0.976) so statistically there was no significant relationship between the wound cleanliness factor and the wound healing process of post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024. The results of this study are not relevant to the research of Atira et al (2021) which stated that the majority (56.7%) of post-appendectomy patients had dirty wounds due to infection so that they experienced a long wound healing process. The results of research by Zielińska et al (2023) stated that dirty wounds or non-aseptic wound care will make it easier for microorganisms to infect post-appendectomy wounds.

Appendectomy is a surgical procedure to remove the appendix (Constantin et al., 2023). The response that arises after an appendectomy is tissue damage and damage to nerve endings and can be at risk of infection if not properly cared for. Surgery is one of the basic components of a very important health care system and has a role in reducing patient suffering from the disease they are suffering from. During the operation process, many microbes enter or accidentally enter the surgical limb, so that these microbes can be bacteria, fungi, viruses and can cause failure to achieve a treatment and cause infection (R Happyanto et al., 2022). Changing bandages that do not comply with aseptic techniques, family or patient compliance in maintaining wound cleanliness, so that the wound becomes dirty and becomes infected (Kurnia et al., 2024).

Wound cleanliness determines whether the wound is free from contamination or signs of infection. If the wound is unclean or infected, an unpleasant odor will develop, indicating a problem and can slow wound healing. According to research conducted by Kheru et al. (2022), the wound healing process involves the integration of various physiological processes. Although the basic nature of healing in all wounds is the same, there are variations depending on the individual's biological condition, the location of the wound, and the severity and extent of the injury.

Surgical wounds require sterile and intensive care to ensure proper post-operative wound healing (Murwaningsih & Waluyo, 2021). Infection prevention procedures include maintaining a clean treatment environment, using aseptic techniques in wound care, and ensuring that instruments and materials used in wound care are sterile. Proper wound care

encompasses several stages. Wounds must be properly cleaned to remove dirt and bacteria that can cause infection (Asyifa et al., 2023). Wound cleansing is typically performed using an antiseptic solution that kills germs without damaging healing tissue. Dressings must be changed regularly and using aseptic techniques to prevent recontamination. Clean bandages help protect wounds from the external environment, which may contain pathogens. Furthermore, medical personnel must be trained to understand and correctly apply aseptic and antiseptic techniques. Better wound care results in cleaner wounds and faster wound healing (Nurjanah et al., 2021).

There is a significant relationship between mobilization factors and the wound healing process of post-appendectomy patients in Pasaman in 2024 with a p value of 0.021. The results of this study are relevant to the research of Darmawan et al. (2024) in their research stating that there is a relationship between early mobilization and post-appendectomy wound healing at Purwokerto Islamic Hospital with a p value of 0.000. Early mobilization in post-appendectomy patients accelerates the patient's wound healing process, thereby reducing the patient's length of stay in the hospital (Rizky Ananda et al., 2021). The results of this study are also relevant to the results of the study of Tazreean et al. (2022) which states that early mobilization is a crucial component of enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) which is very effective in the post-appendectomy wound healing process.

At Pasaman Hospital, early mobilization for post-appendectomy patients is implemented six hours after surgery. Patients are taught deep breathing techniques, alternating leg lifts, and right and left tilts. When the patient cooperates, gradual mobilization activities are advanced, such as sitting in bed, standing, and walking a few steps. An explanation of early mobilization is provided before the patient consents to surgery. Early mobilization improves and facilitates blood circulation, ensuring adequate nutrient supply to the wound tissue and accelerating the healing process (Daulay & Simamora, 2019). Early mobilization improves and facilitates blood circulation, which is expected to increase nutrient supply to the wound tissue, thereby accelerating the healing process.

Early mobilization can support the wound healing process in patients because moving the limbs can prevent muscle and joint stiffness, reduce pain, and improve blood flow to the injured area, thus accelerating wound healing (Widodo & Qoniah, 2020). Early mobilization is a policy to immediately help patients get out of bed and walk. Early mobilization is crucial for accelerating the treatment period and reducing the risks associated with prolonged bed rest,

such as stiffness or muscle tension throughout the body and impaired blood circulation. Several factors can contribute to delayed mobilization and poor adherence to early mobilization recommendations. First, delayed early mobilization due to poor patient consciousness, such as delirium or other surgical complications (Grass et al., 2018). Several preoperative risk factors also contribute to delayed mobilization, including advanced age, physical/performance status, and malnutrition (Thanh et al., 2020). Early mobilization activities can be facilitated by health workers by conditioning the patient such as removing urinary catheters, removing intravenous catheters and optimal pain management (Tazreean et al., 2022).

Anemia in post-appendectomy patients has a significant relationship with the wound healing process, with a p value of 0.016. The results of this study are relevant to the results of the study by Miles & Richards (2022) which stated that preoperative anemia significantly affects the post-operative wound healing process because intravenous iron therapy is needed before surgery. The results of the study by Gorelik et al (2021) that anemia significantly affects the post-operative wound healing process and catholyte therapy is very effective in treating anemia and is able to increase the body's immunity. The study by Pasaribu & Faradina (2024) showed a significant relationship between anemia, body mass index (BMI), and early mobilization on wound healing after Caesarean section, with the results of the Chi-Square test showing a p value = 0.02 ($\alpha < 0.05$), which means there is a significant relationship between anemia and the wound healing process.

The healing process for appendectomy wounds generally involves several stages: blood clotting, inflammation, new tissue formation, and tissue maturation or strengthening (Kurnia et al., 2024). Red blood cells play a crucial role in this process, delivering oxygen and nutrients for post-surgical tissue repair. However, other factors influence wound healing time, such as the type of surgery, wound size, tissue damage, and the presence of other comorbidities (Constantin et al., 2023). Anemia reduces the oxygen and nutrients needed for cell regeneration and new tissue formation (Arribas-López et al., 2021). Cells in the body require oxygen to function optimally, especially during wound healing, which involves cell division and new tissue formation. When tissue oxygenation is impaired, wound healing is slow and ineffective (Miles & Richards, 2022). Furthermore, anemia can weaken the immune system, making the body more susceptible to infection. Wound infections can lead to serious complications, slow the healing process, and increase the risk of morbidity (Claresta, 2019). The study found that only a small percentage, 19

(38%), experienced post-appendectomy anemia. However, 10 of these individuals experienced prolonged wound healing, while the remaining 9 experienced good wound healing. Therefore, it can be assumed that anemia affects post-appendectomy wound healing, but this depends on the severity of the patient's anemia.

There are several factors that influence the wound healing process after appendectomy surgery, namely nutritional status, wound hygiene, early mobilization, and anemia. Based on the results of the multivariate final logistic regression model analysis, it is known that the most dominant factor influencing the wound healing process is anemia with a p value of 0.009 ($p < 0.05$). From the analysis results, an Odd Ratio (OR) value of 7.628 was obtained, meaning that anemia has a 7.628 times chance of slowing the wound healing process in post-appendectomy patients compared to other factors. The results of this study are relevant to the results of the study by Kheru et al (2022) which stated that anemia is a dominant factor in inhibiting the wound healing process because anemia is a condition in which the number of red blood cells or hemoglobin in the body is less than normal, which results in a reduced ability of the blood to transport oxygen to body tissues, thus disrupting various aspects of health including wound healing. This contradicts the results of the study by Pasaribu & Faradina (2024) which stated that the dominant factor influencing the post-op wound healing process is the early mobilization factor. In the results of this study, early mobilization is also a factor that greatly influences the wound healing process after anemia.

Anemia is the most dominant factor in the wound healing process due to its systemic nature. If a patient experiences severe anemia, they will indirectly be unable to mobilize early and maintain personal hygiene. The patient's immune system will be weakened, making them susceptible to infection, which will affect the wound healing process after an appendectomy. Post-op patients are often immobile due to potential post-operative complications and activity restrictions, putting the patient's physical capacity at risk of decreasing (Tustumi et al., 2020). To maintain optimal condition despite limitations, patients are required to continue to be able to independently perform self-care. This can be realized through the nursing theory developed by Dorothea E. Orem on self-care.

CONCLUSION

Factors influencing the post-appendectomy wound healing process include nutritional status, wound hygiene, early mobilization, and anemia. The most

dominant factor is anemia. Implementing Orem's self-care model can significantly impact the nursing process, particularly in post-appendectomy cases, in addressing issues related to meeting daily needs. Implementing this model can be beneficial in encouraging patients to engage in activities appropriate to their abilities and tolerance, thereby addressing any factors hindering the wound healing process.

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